

IDIOSTIL VA UNING LINGVOPOETIK O'ZIGA XOSLIGI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola bugungi o'zbek va jaxon tilshunosligida lingvopoetika tushunchasining mohiyati xususida so'z yuritib, uni idiosstil yondashuvi bilan bog'laydi. Maqolada o'zbek va jahon tilshunosligida va ayniqsa, adabiyotshunosligida lingvopoetika haqidagi qarashlar va yondashuvlar haqida fikr yuritiladi. Fikrlarni ilmiy asoslash uchun turli yozuvchi va shoirlar ijodiy uslubidan namunalar keltiriladi va izohlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: idiosstil, lingvopoetika, kognitiv tilshunoslik, lingvokulturologiya, qiyoslash, umulashtirish, qiyosiy tahlil, janr, muallif nutqi, muallifning individual yozish uslubi

INTRODUCTION

The language of literary works has always been at the center of attention for both linguistic and literary fields. Because "linguistic picture of the world" discovered the antropocentric view to the world by the author's worldview and his language.

Indeed, there are numerous writers and poets in the world and each one has their own writing styles which rarely repeat each other. They create their works according to the time, global theme of the time, cultural views, tradition and customs and national and religious beliefs, national folk heroes and moral values.

METHODS

Because of these reasons, literary works differ considerably from each other. And that term is analysed as "idiostyle" or "individual style" in the field of linguistics and literature. Here, we consider it worthwhile to note that the vast majority of researchers consider the terms "individual style" and "idiostyle" as synonymous, but some still state that notion of "idiostyle" is more modern than "individual style" since it means new and broader, according to its content, linguistic phenomenon⁴. In fact, the initial research on the author's idiostyle began in the 50-60 years of the twentieth century, although the exact term idiostyle was not used at that time. Only in V. V. Vinogradov's studies the term idiostyle was originally used in linguistics as introduced by a Russian linguist V.P. Grigoriev.

RESULTS

This term includes the method of expressing a specific opinion of the author of speech and the meanings of mastery of the use of linguistic means. Later, idiostyle was interpreted as a phenomenon that expresses the specific signs of author's speech.

As the first research work in Uzbek linguistics aimed at the study of author's idiostyle, it is possible to indicate S. Umirova's dissertation. She studies the idiostyle in his own thesis under the term poetic individuality, and states that "the cause of the individual skill of the creator, each language material used in the text can become a poetic unity and an individual tool inherent only in this creative style. Lingvopoetic studies are considered a specific peak of allphilological research and for him, the higher status opportunities of language, which are a high expression of human feelings, are taken as an object of observation."

According to the definition by Fomenko, idiostyle of the writer is a communicative and cognitive space of linguistic personality which creates artistic discourse modelling a lingvo-typological variant of the literary text of a certain period⁵. Indeed, idiostyle as a definitely organised structure. It is a combination of inner textforming dominants and

⁴ Bolotnova, N. S. (2009). *Kommunikativnaya stilistika teksta: slovar-tezaurus* [Communicative Stylistics of the Text]. Moscow, Russia: Flinta, Nauka.

⁵ Fomenko, Je. G. (2006). *Lingvotipologicheskoye v idiostile Dzheyma Dzhoysa* [Linguo-Typological Properties of James Joyce's Idiostyle]. Extended abstract of PhD dissertation, Zaporozhye, Ukraine.

constants while highlighting four types of its structural elements: situational, conceptual, operational and compositional “metatropes” that are the framework of the author’s individual style and form a hierarchically ordered but, at the same time, closed system. Because the study of idiostylistic features of the author must also take into account individual, socio-historical, national, psychological, moral and ethical norms of a certain period, the peculiarities of the world perception of a person and knowledge about the world, which the researcher perceives as a unique author's conceptual picture of the world. Surely, individual style of the author is not only relevant to the linguistic means, such as words, phrases, expressions, figures of speech. But, first of all, an author’s feeling about his work as an artistic creation and the morality of the work which is perceived by readers are much more important.

Certainly, all level units of the language, such as phonetic-phonological, morphemic, lexical, morphological, syntactic and even supersyntactic, are involved in the expression of artistic meaning in the work. But it should be noted that all of these units, without exception, do not directly and uniformly serve the artistic intention of the writer. Some of these units receive special artistic-aesthetic emphasis in a certain favorable artistic context created by the writer according to his writing skill level.

The basis of linguopoetic analysis is the same principle, with the principle of identifying the work poetically. Due to the extensive attention paid to the study of the language of artistic works in the linguistics of the 20th century, the term "lingupoetics" appeared, reflecting the comprehensive, deep and comprehensive study of the image of reality in the artistic work, combining the concepts of rhetoric and poetics.

In fact, linguopoetics is a large field of philology that studies stylistically marked linguistic units used in the creative work by a writer in terms of their functions and relative value in giving the artistic content and creating aesthetic effect in readers’ imagination.

For example:

When we read the works of Utkir Hoshimov, the most prominent writer of uzbek people, at the first glance, we can feel his idiostyle, as the theme of his works is mostly related to war (Nur borki, soya bor, Urushning so’nggi qurboni, Dunyoning ishlari, Ikki

eshik orasi and others). In these works, the author raises important moral and ethical issues of the time, revealing the flaws in the social life of society, the essence of stagnation with the same heroes in each work. He tries to express the whole difficulty of the with only several heroes in simple words, he does not use colourful words and expressive emotions as in the example, which shows the real idiosyncrasy of the writer.

- Ertalab-chi, oyi, yomg'ir yog'di. Qattiq yomg'ir yog'di. Siz bahor yomg'irini yaxshi ko'radingiz... Keyin oftob chiqib ketdi. Qarang, oftob charaqlab yotibdi... Esingizdami, siz menga oftob to'g'risida cho'pchak aytib bergan edingiz. O'sha oftob charaqlab yotibdi... Ko'ryapsizmi...⁶

- It rained in the morning. It rained heavily. You loved the spring rain... Then the sun came out. Look, the sun is shining... Do you remember when you told me about the sun? That sun is shining... Do you see...

If we pay attention to the linguistic style, it is short and simple. The linguistic tools, that is to say, words of the work are so clear that even translating, one has no difficulty. Because the artistic intention of the writer is to express the artistic content with folk linguistic units.

CONCLUSION

Although linguopoetics is a wide subject, its studied aspect is still of very little value in Uzbek linguistics and literature. Its development and research will be very valuable to young writers and the field of linguistics in the future.

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⁶ Utkir Hoshimov, The work "Dunyoning Ishlari", Tashkent 2005, p 208

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